

Epigraphy.info IX Workshop: Final Report

Authors:

Elena Duce Pastor, University Autonoma of Madrid, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0604-2300>

Cristina de la Escosura, University of Alcalá, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1769-657X>

Petra Heřmánková, Aarhus University, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6349-0540>

Silvia Evangelisti, University of Foggia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7186-9518>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15705466>

Next workshop:

Spring 2026, Prof. Wolfgang Spickermann of the University of Graz

The current Steering Committee members [2025-2026]:

- Georgios Tsolakis, The University of Chicago, USA
- Rebecca Benefiel, Washington and Lee University, USA
- Marina Bastero Acha, University of Warsaw, PL
- Silvia Evangelisti, University of Foggia, IT
- Winfried Kumpitsch, University of Graz, AUT
- Annie Burman, Uppsala University, SWE
- Andrea Santamaria, Kiel University, DE

Contact: info@epigraphy.info (Steering Committee)

Social Media: [Instagram](#), [Facebook](#), [X/Twitter](#), [YouTube](#)

Epigraphy.info community on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/epigraphy-info/>

Link to the report from the Epigraphy VIII <https://zenodo.org/records/12514368>

Link to the Epigraphy IX collaborative document [Epigraphy-info-9-Aarhus-shared-doc](#)

Introduction

[Epigraphy.info](#) is an international, open community that fosters a collaborative environment for digital epigraphy, facilitating scholarly communication and interaction. Epigraphy.info applies FAIR principles to epigraphic information, enabling the efficient creation, use, and sharing of it among researchers, students, and enthusiasts worldwide. The Epigraphy.info community works to gather and enhance the many existing epigraphic efforts and serves as a landing point for digital tools, practices and methodologies for managing collections of inscriptions.

The Epigraphy.info conference traditionally brings together researchers and enthusiasts of digital epigraphy to discuss the current trends and issues of the discipline. The meeting includes academic presentations on various topics in digital epigraphy and challenges of the current research, and poster session, as well as training hands-on sessions and workshops/hackathons of the existing working groups and interactive roundtables. It provides a safe space for networking, learning, developing new collaborations, and cutting-edge research in ancient studies, expanding the discipline's traditional Greek and Latin focus to include runic studies, Mayan epigraphy, and Egyptian

hieroglyphs. Since the establishment of Epigraphy.info in 2018, there have been eight international meetings: Heidelberg, DE, 2018; Zadar, CRO, 2018; Vienna, AUT, 2019; Hamburg, DE, 2020; Leuven (online), BE, 2020; Princeton (online), US, 2021; Leuven, BE, 2023; Berlin, DE, 2024.

The ninth Epigraphy.info workshop took place in Aarhus (Denmark) from 2-4 April 2025; see the website at https://epigraphy.info/workshop_9. The workshop was hosted by the [Past Social Network Project](#) and the [Social Resilience Lab](#), Department of History and Classical Studies, and the Museum of Ancient Art at Aarhus University. In collaboration with the Past Social Networks Project from Aarhus University, special attention was given to the application of network science in epigraphy, culminating in a special session on Social networks and epigraphy and a hands-on session on reconstructing the social networks from inscriptions.

A total of 117 participants registered for the Epigraphy.info IX, including 72 in person and 45 online attendees. The in-person participants represent remarkable diversity, coming from 13 different countries across Europe and North America: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Spain, Sweden, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. The gender distribution shows most female participants (61%), with 36% male, 1.4% genderqueer, and 1.4% preferring not to disclose their gender. In terms of career stages, the workshop has attracted participants across the academic spectrum: 34.7% are undergraduate or master's students, 9.7% are doctoral candidates, 27.8% are Early Career Researchers (including postdoctoral fellows and assistant professors), 23.6% are Senior Researchers (including associate and full professors, senior researchers, and those in management roles), and 4.2% reported other professional backgrounds. The number of online participants varied from 10 to 15 people, depending on the session.

DAY 1: 2 April 2025

On the morning of April 2, three different **hands-on sessions** were held in parallel in the morning from 9:00 to 12:00.

1. Winfried Kumpitsch and Wolfgang Spickermann presented the project *Celtic Divine Names in Latin Inscriptions in the southern region of Germania Superior and in the province of Raetia*.
2. Chiara Cenati, Silvia Evangelisti and Francisca Feraudi Gruenais, in the session *Encoding Verse Inscriptions in MetrICa and MAPPOLA*, explained the purposes and methods of coding verse inscriptions underway for MetrICa, the current coding possibilities offered by EdEp, and then dwelt more extensively on MAPPOLA, which the session participants were able to experiment with.
3. Petra Heřmánková and Tom Brughmans, in the session *Reconstructing the Past Social Networks from Inscriptions: Practical Hands-on Session*, demonstrated practical methodologies and computational tools, specifically using the R programming language, for reconstructing historical social networks from inscriptions. Participants engaged with two hands-on examples based on epigraphic data. The first exercise involved reconstructing a multi-generational family network, allowing participants to experiment with various visualisation techniques. The second, more complex case study focused on a kinship network from Pompeii, providing an opportunity to explore and apply basic analytical measures in network analysis.

After the lunch break, the local organisers, Petra Heřmánková and Tom Brughmans welcomed participants back by providing practical information about the meeting and introducing the research activities of the project they are both involved. This project, the [Past Social Networks Project](#), co-organiser of the event, is part of the Core Collective, a computational humanities research environment based at the Faculty of Arts, Aarhus University.

The introduction was followed by the **first keynote lecture**, delivered in person by [Jessica Munson](#), with [Matthew Looper](#) as co-author. Their talk, titled *Royal Titles and Ritual Traditions in Classic Maya Monumental Inscriptions*, examined the distribution and diversity of royal titles in Classic Maya hieroglyphic inscriptions. By analysing how these titles were represented, they explored the organisation and expression of ancient Maya governance. To interpret the observed patterns of variation, Munson and Looper proposed that ritual practices were closely tied to different forms of governance. This approach enabled them to construct a ritual network, identifying clusters of sites based on ritual similarities. Using multivariate analysis, they further investigated the diversity of rituals practised by various groups and how these practices correlated with the distribution of royal titles.

After the coffee break, the **first Social Network session** commenced, featuring three presentations that explored the application of network analysis in the study of inscriptions:

- [Francesca Mazzilli](#) and [José Carlos López-Gómez](#) presented on the *Interplay between Religious, Social, and Spatial Networks in Lusitania and Baetica*, examining how different types of networks intersected in these Roman provinces.
- [Christina Videbech](#) delivered a talk titled *Networks of Faith: Mapping Early Christian Interaction and Identity through the Christian Graffiti of Rome's Central Fora (4th–8th centuries CE)*, highlighting how inscriptions can reveal patterns of religious identity and interaction.
- [Christoph Klose](#) and [Wolfgang Filser](#) presented *Villas as Nodes: Social Networks Evolving from the Results of the Excavations at the Maritime Villa of Capo di Sorrento*, discussing how archaeological findings inform our understanding of elite social networks in Roman coastal contexts.

The day concluded with a **reception at the Antikmuseet**, which was catered and warmly hosted by the museum. The evening began with a welcome address by museum director Vinnie Nørskov, followed by a guided presentation of the exhibition Roman Connections by Tom Brughmans. The exhibition offered participants a chance to explore Roman-era artifacts and themes, including puzzling Christian inscriptions from ancient Carthage, in a relaxed and engaging setting, rounding off the day's academic program with a cultural highlight.

DAY 2: 3 April 2025

After a catered breakfast with Danish bread and cheese, David Eibeck chaired the morning session, **Metric inscriptions & standards**, featuring three in-person presentations and one online.

The first talk by [Silvia Evangelisti](#) (in person) and [Pietro Liuzzo](#) (online) talked about *MetrICA - reuse and cooperation in digital epigraphy*. The MetrICA Project <https://metricaproject.it/>

focuses on inscriptions in Campania. It started with a congress titled Encoding Metrical Inscriptions 14-15 novembre 2024 ([programme](#)) in which both researchers realised that they had similar problems with other metrical encoders (i.e., Mappola). So, they created two documents, Encoding with [EdEp](#) and shared them with the community.

1. The session continued with Gianmarco Bianchini (in person) and [Rebecca Benefiel](#) (online), who spoke in the last workshop in Berlin. They presented *Finding the poetry in ancient graffiti*, a Collaboration between the Ancient Graffiti Project (<https://ancientgraffiti.org/Graffiti/>), MetrICa, and EDR. This collaboration began during spring 2024 and runs through fall 2025, and had the aim to incorporate students from courses to projects from different backgrounds (as Silvia Orlandi suggested). This proposal led the community to a discussion about the importance of collaboration and the incorporation of unreadable characters, and Marietta Horster mentioned different options to have funding.
2. The third presentation, *Documenting inscriptions: a CIDOC CRM based model for epigraphical data documentation* [virtual] by [Eleni Sfyridou](#) and [Georgios Papaioannou](#). It presented a case study about the Rosetta Stone and how to create an ontological-based model.
3. The session finished with [Annie Burman](#) (in person) and the presentation titled *Etruscans in the Archive: Disseminating an epigraphist's archive in the digital age*. This on-course Project (<https://www.alvin-portal.org/>) promoted a lively discussion about what material type a squeeze was and how to mark up squeezes properly. She is creating a front-end to drive people searching for Etruscan squeezes to Alvin. During the discussion, Jonathan Prag suggested alignment with existing LOD, such as Getty vocabularies (useful link: Getty AAT squeeze: <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300451052>).

After a coffee break, everybody was invited to join one of the **working group meetings** to present their roles and future decisions. This meeting aimed to create the final report for the end of the workshop.

- During the **Ontologies & Vocabularies** WG meeting, Petra Heřmánková and Jonathan Prag presented the FAIR Epigraphy draft of the epigraphic ontology (current draft available via [MIRO board](#)) and FAIR Epigraphy vocabularies at <https://ontology.inscriptiones.org/index.html> (work in progress), and invited any feedback.
- The **Communication & Outreach** WG meeting, presented by Chiara Cenati, explained their roles and included two new members (https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qojchCw19r0n1gG2mlfO1Ve6uJxyULEI5cvRg_zCSK18/edit?tab=t.0)
- In the **Funding** WG meeting, Francisca Feraudi-Gruénais revised the past actions of the group. They managed to support the DAMOS Project to have new funding and decided to divide the working group to have local advisors in different countries.

The afternoon was divided into three parts: the second session on social networks, the poster session and a round-table discussion.

The **second Social Networks session** was chaired by Tomas Glomb, with four in-person presentations.

1. The first speakers, [Petra Hermankova](#), [Matteo Mazzamurro](#), [Michele Coscia](#) and [Tom Brughmans](#), presented *The Economic Complexity of the Roman Empire seen through Inscriptions*. Their work takes into account economic complexity (ECI) derived from the instances of occupations on inscriptions. Their approach includes computationally assisted correction of known biases (gender, research, status, etc.) in order to detect and map the occupational diversity of the Roman Empire, using modern analytical methods. They reiterated the importance of having open data, lemmatisation tools, vocabularies and tagging occupations in EpiDoc, so any similar projects can utilise the great wealth of epigraphic data.
2. [Melinda Szabó](#) continued with *Social and Business Relations along the Amber Road*. She presented her Project about the merchant inscriptions in Pannonia and the visualisation with [Gephi](#).
3. The third speaker, [Eleonora Selvi](#), presented *Multivariate SNA and linguistic choices: an analysis of funerary inscriptions from Hellenistic Pamphylia*. The combination of inscriptions in multiple languages led to a discussion about emigration and the expansion of Greek. She pointed out that there is no relationship between the Greek family names and the expansion of koiné. Thus, the creation of personal names is wide, and they use a mix of roots from Greek, Anatolian, and Egyptian. She also presented examples of more than one alphabet per inscription.
4. Finally, [Andrea Santamaria](#) closed the session with *Social Network Analysis and the materiality of writing: a case study from 2nd-millennium BCE Cretan Hieroglyphic seals*. Working with a very specific and complex material, he presented the problem of the readability of the seals, their dispersion, and social networks related to seal scribes.

The **poster session** ran from 14:30-16:00, allowing ample time for attendees to engage with all the contributions. All poster information can be accessed at https://epigraphy.info/workshop_9_posters/, and several contributions have been published as part of the Zenodo Epigraphy.info community, each assigned a unique DOI for citation and long-term accessibility.

The day ended with an hour-long **Roundtable discussion, From EAGLE to LOD: Examining FAIR and Sustainable Practices in Digital Epigraphy**, with some of the participants joining remotely. List of participants: [Marietta Horster](#) (in person), [Jonathan Prag](#) (in person), [Silvia Orlandi](#) (in person), [Rebecca Benefiel](#) (online), [Sara Sprenkle](#) (online), [Mark Depauw](#) (audio), [Petra Hermankova](#) (in person), and [Imran Asif](#) (online).

The roundtable brought together leading voices in digital epigraphy to reflect on the field's progress over recent years and to critically assess both achievements and ongoing challenges. Each speaker shared personal insights, evaluations, and proposals for the future.

Jonathan Prag opened with a positive reflection on the field's evolution since the 2019 Vienna workshop. He highlighted significant progress in areas once considered intractable—such as vocabularies, identifiers, and bibliographic standards—thanks to innovative solutions and growing consensus. However, he acknowledged persistent challenges, particularly in institutional communication and overcoming cultural barriers.

Marietta Horster emphasised the advancements made through the Epigraphy.info initiative, including the development of FAIR Epigraphy since the first workshop in Heidelberg in 2018 https://epigraphy.info/workshop_1. She stressed the importance of involving IT professionals, like software engineer Imran Asif, in building robust digital infrastructures. She also raised concerns about the time-consuming nature of citation and called for community-wide efforts to streamline bibliographic practices. Marietta proposed opening discussions with major projects like Trismegistos and EAGLE, and advocated for a more strategic allocation of funding.

Mark Depauw from the [Trismegistos](#) project sent a short video, where he focused on the need for identifiers, cautioning against over-regulation. He argued that future discussions should prioritise project content over rigid rule-making.

Drawing on 15 years of experience, Silvia Orlandi highlighted the roles of luck and effort in successful digital projects (e.g., [EAGLE](#)). She warned against mismanaging funding and advocated for using resources to train scholars and foster independence. Silvia also emphasised the importance of high-quality content as the foundation of any digital initiative.

Rebecca Benefiel, in collaboration with Sara Sprenkle (technical lead of [AGP](#)), discussed the importance of student training, particularly in the U.S. context, where such opportunities are limited. She outlined plans to broaden access to graffiti editions and integrate FAIR principles and Linked Open Data (LOD). Rebecca also raised concerns about AI's impact on attribution, a key component of the R in FAIR (Reusability).

Jonathan returned to discuss Nomisma, emphasising a do it and they will follow approach. He advocated for collaboration and professional training that goes beyond introductory digital epigraphy.

The session concluded with an engaging discussion involving the audience:

- Cristina de la Escosura addressed institutional and financial barriers to hiring IT professionals.
- Francisca Feraudi stressed the need to communicate institutional needs clearly and to invest in student training.
- Adela Sobotkova presented a Scandinavian networking grant aimed at student exchange and training.
- Tom Brughmans proposed creating a pool of internship opportunities across projects.
- Silvia Orlandi emphasised the necessity of financial support for such exchanges.
- Marietta Horster highlighted Erasmus+ as a valuable funding source for student training, such as stays from two to six months at another University.
- Joe Sheppard mentioned additional opportunities for graduate students and early-career researchers.
- Annie Burman introduced a new discussion on documentation and good data practices in digital epigraphy. Key themes included:
 - The role of Linked Open Data (LOD).
 - The inclusion of Greek inscriptions in digital projects.
 - The need to teach attribution.
 - The potential of AI to standardise data, with a reminder that accurate, not necessarily complete, data is essential for training AI models.
 - The importance of creating teaching content to support the next generation of digital epigraphers.

After the productive day, participants continued their discussions during the walk and the social dinner that followed.

Day 3: 4 April 2025

The last day started with the **keynote lecture** by Laila Kitzler Åhfeld from the Swedish National Heritage Board on runic inscriptions, titled '*Runestones and the quest for social networks: tracing the carvers by 3D-analysis*'. For the presentation, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15223562>. The talk sparked a great discussion of applied methodology to study the carving technology and the epigraphic cultures of Scandinavia, which could be potentially used also in the Mediterranean environment.

The morning session titled **New Insights**, chaired by Thea Sommerschild, contained two talks discussing new approaches to the well-known materials.

1. [Tomas Glomb](#) and [Sebastian Kheml](#) from the Masaryk University presented '*The impact of Malaria on the spatial distribution of inscriptions dedicated to Asclepius in the Roman Empire*'. They approach the existing literary and epigraphic sources (mostly Latin), to discover the impact of the diffusion of malaria on society and its religious beliefs, as preserved by epigraphy.
2. [Joe Sheppard](#) from the Ashmolean Museum gave a talk '*Integrating Numismatics and Epigraphy: The Roman Provincial Coinage Online and EpiDoc Project at the Ashmolean Museum (Oxford)*', <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15211389>, discussing the current application of OpenAI to automate the interpretation of coin legends and its applicability for the field of epigraphy.

The second session of the morning, **(New) Projects**, chaired by Elena Duce Pastor, contained one talk in person and three prerecorded remote talks.

1. [Cristina de la Escosura Balbás](#) from the University of Alcalá gave an update on the status of the Hispania Epigraphica Online, titled '*Hispania Epigraphica Online: life, problems and future of funded databases*'. After challenging times in 2024, the database is now available online at <https://hepol.uah.es/>, supported by the University of Alcalá. Cristina brought attention to the need for sustainability measures within the discipline, which sparked a great discussion and resonated throughout the rest of the conference. One possible solution is to use Zenodo as a backup repository for our data, following the principles of FAIR and Open Science.
2. The series of online talks was initiated by [Dimitar Iliev](#) and [Nicolay Sharankov](#) from St. Kliment Ohridski University in Sofia, presenting the '*Epigraphic storytelling in collaboration: the PROMETHEUS Project*'. The Prometheus Project <https://prometheus-epigraphy.eu/> is a network of digital epigraphy projects in North Macedonia, Bulgaria, and Serbia. The project is developing a storytelling platform, Promoting Universal Values through Digital Epigraphy and Cultural Heritage, co-funded by the EU in 2024-2025.
3. The next talk by [Beatrice Luci](#) from the Sapienza University of Rome, titled '*From stone to web: MADE and the dissemination of Medieval Epigraphy*', presented the MADE: Middle Ages' Digital Epigraphy Project <https://www.madedb.it/> and some of the challenges with outreach online and on social media, with a series of videos and short talks. They introduce the Adopt an inscription feature to help connect the interested public with the experts.

4. [Daria Russo](#) from the CNRS gave a talk titled *SculpSi. A Digital Edition of Greek and Roman Sculptors' Signatures (323 BCE-138 CE). Project presentation*, presenting the SculpSi project <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101108453>, funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) in 2023-2025. The project focuses on the reconstruction of SculpSi, which focuses on sculptors' signatures found at the works of Greek and Roman sculptors between the Hellenistic period and the reign of Hadrian (323 BCE-138 CE) in the areas corresponding to Roman Italy and the provinces of Achaia and Asia.

Community discussion and decisions

The afternoon session was dedicated to community discussion and reports from the working groups, community decisions, and most importantly, the Steering Committee election and choosing of the organiser of the next meeting in 2026.

Next workshop:

There was one candidate for the local organiser of the Epigraphy.info X workshop. The community has approved that the next workshop will be organised by Prof. Wolfgang Spickermann of the University of Graz. The exact date will be communicated later, but presumably in spring 2026.

The Steering Committee election:

As three steering committee members were stepping down (David Eibeck, Elena Duce Pastor, and Jonathan Prag), the community had to select three new members. In the end, four candidates are elected as new members: Silvia Evangelisti, Winfried Kumpitsch, Annie Burman, and Andrea Santamaria. The new Steering Committee has therefore 7 members:

- Georgios Tsolakis, The University of Chicago, USA
- Rebecca Benefiel, Washington and Lee University, USA
- Marina Bastero Acha, University of Warsaw, PL
- Silvia Evangelisti, University of Foggia, IT
- Winfried Kumpitsch, University of Graz, AUT
- Annie Burman, Uppsala University, SWE
- Andrea Santamaria, Kiel University, DE

Ontology & Vocabularies Working Group Report:

- activities organised by the FAIR Epigraphy Project (funded until 02/2026), new ontology in progress (J. Prag), new vocabularies in progress (P. Heřmánková), see more at <https://inscripciones.org/>

Communication & Outreach Working Group Report:

- Hosting of the Epigraphy.info domain will be transferred from Brigitte Graf to Petra Heřmánková, and will stay under the <https://www.united-domains.de/>. The website will still be accessible via GitHub Pages at <https://epigraphy.info/> and managed by Petra Heřmánková, with contributions by the trained WG members. The costs of the hosting [35 EUR per year + 15 EUR one-time fee for transfer of the owner] will be covered by funds collected from individual donations at Aarhus. A similar crowdfunding campaign will likely repeat at future meetings. The Past Social

Networks Project has offered to cover 1 year of hosting fees, so the current funds will easily last until the next meeting in 2026.

- Website reorganisation: In 2025, a minor reorganisation of the website will happen, led by the WG in collaboration with Petra Heřmánková. The changes mostly concern the membership and projects
- Current Epigraphy: David Eibeck will continue to act as a manager

Funding Working Group Report:

- Need for a centralised contact point to disseminate calls for funding, etc.
- Revision of access to the shared Google folders. In 2025, SC and WG will revise access, based on the updated memberships of WGS, SC and Epigraphy.info